

Joint Action on integrating prevention, testing and linkage to care strategies across HIV, viral hepatitis, TB and STIs in Europe

WP 7.2 Partner Notification Mapping Exercise

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Executive Summary

The joint action Integrate aims to increase integrated early diagnosis and linkage to prevention and care across HIV, STIs, viral hepatitis and TB in EU member states. One arm of the joint action addresses partner notification / contact tracing as a prevention tool. Partner notification not only helps prevent re-infection for the index patient but also contributes to increased linkage to care through the referral of at-risk individuals that benefit from testing and services.

Integrate will run a pilot study to improve partner notification outcomes in Ireland, Italy, Romania and Greece. This report maps the pathways and practices of partner notification/ contact tracing across the four disease areas in planned pilot countries. Through key informant interviews in the respective healthcare settings, the report highlights barriers, facilitators, tools and pathways of PN/CT as well as potential for integrating the four disease areas, ensuring that the pilot study effectively addresses key issues for each participating JA partner.

The interviews demonstrated a general confusion among healthcare providers in respect to PN/CT; not only on the official legal requirements and available guidelines, but also on how PN/CT is conducted on the ground. This is often compounded by a lack of uniform set-up for partner notification across countries and healthcare systems. An even more pressing barrier, noted unanimously, is a lack of resources and time to ensure that partner notification is handled appropriately and effectively.

Across sites and disease areas it was suggested that increased training on and awareness of partner notification could improve outcomes. Healthcare workers need training on partner notification, and the laws that surround it in their specific context, to feel confident in conducting and counselling patients on the topic. Despite the differences in healthcare contexts or disease areas, increased training could be applied to numerous settings.

While this report hoped to highlight the potential integration of HIV, STIs, viral hepatitis and TB, this may not be possible. The main challenge arises when attempting to integrate TB with the other disease areas. While HIV, STIs and hepatitis are often cared for within the realm of infectious diseases, TB tends to be housed in pneumology departments. Additionally, as the route of transmission for TB is different, it follows that the contract tracing methods for TB must be structured in a different way. Coupled together, there are few areas for integration, with experts noting that it would be very difficult, and perhaps unwarranted, to do so. Despite many differences, the interviews demonstrate that TB is typically the most developed PN/CT programme out of all the diseases, with a history of established pathways and national guidelines, offering the potential to learn from TB CT for other disease areas. Offering training for TB contact tracing may still be applicable to improve outcomes but finding one uniform method of partner notification/ contact tracing across the four disease areas is unlikely to affect change.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	5
1. Introduction	7
2. Ireland	8
2.1 HIV and STIs	8
2.2 Viral Hepatitis	9
2.3 Tuberculosis	10
2.4 Areas of Potential Integration/ Overlap	11
2.4 Flowchart Ireland	13
3. Italy	14
3.1 HIV/STIs	14
3.2 Viral Hepatitis	15
3.3 Tuberculosis	15
3.4 Areas of Potential Integration/ Overlap	16
3.5 Flowchart Italy	17
4. Romania	18
4.1 HIV/STIs	18
4.2 Viral Hepatitis	19
4.3 Tuberculosis	19
4.4 Areas of Potential Integration/Overlap	20
4.5 Flowchart Romania	21
5. Greece	22
5.1 HIV/STIs	22
5.2 Viral Hepatitis	23
5.3 Tuberculosis	23
5.4 Areas of Potential Integration/Overlap	24
5.5 Flowchart Greece	26
6. Conclusions	27
Bibliography	29
Abbreviations	30

1. Introduction

The joint action Integrate aims to increase integrated early diagnosis and linkage to prevention and care across HIV, STIs, viral hepatitis and TB in EU member states. Work Package 7 objective 2 aims to improve the use of partner notification (known as contact tracing in TB) as secondary prevention tool. In 2013, the ECDC released a report on partner notification in Europe [1], providing an overview of current partner notification policies and practices in Europe, evaluating the role of partner notification in public health prevention efforts.

The mapping exercise updates the work already done by the ECDC[1] through the Dublin monitoring on the mapping of legal barriers and facilitators to partner notification/ contact tracing (PN/CT) practices for HIV, viral hepatitis, TB and STIs across Europe. This exercise will inform the pilot study to be conducted in four Integrate partner countries and be used as the foundation for organizing the pilot studies for improving PN/CT outcomes.

To effectively address the aims of the joint action Integrate, the first step required mapping the pathways and barriers that currently exist in the Integrate partner countries around Europe. This will help identify the most pressing needs and opportunities within the different healthcare systems to affect change in the PN/CT processes. This report intends to map different components of partner notification across the pilot study countries: Ireland, Italy, Romania and Greece.

The report utilized key informant interviews to inform about logistics, coordination, circuits/ pathways, tools, economic barriers, professional roles and local guidelines in each pilot country. Key informants from each disease group were interviewed to gain an understanding of how partner notification pathways operate in day-to-day life.

2. Ireland

This section aims to identify and explore the pathways, barriers, and guidelines for HIV, STIs, viral hepatitis and TB in The Republic of Ireland.

2.1 HIV and STIs

In Ireland, HIV and STIs follow the same pathways throughout partner notification, and so they will be discussed together here. The main difference between the two areas being that with an HIV diagnosis, a general practitioner (GP) is more likely to be involved in conversations about and the process of partner notification, although this is not always the case.

2.1.1 Pathways

The Department of Health is not involved with partner notification (PN) for HIV/STIs, as each county has been historically responsible for creating and overseeing their own strategy and process. Due to this, there is no set pathway for partner notification nationally. Common guidance within Ireland states that the person in charge of delivering the diagnosis to the patient manages the partner notification, yet this does not outline who will be conducting it or discussing it directly with the patient. In reality, GPs do not conduct PN, and will refer patients to an STI clinic for PN services. Within larger clinics, dedicated health advisors are responsible for PN, while in smaller or rural clinics the task falls to specialist nurses.

However, despite guidelines noting it should be done, PN is not prioritized, nor is it given any devoted time for nurses to conduct it. Healthcare workers are meant to encourage patients to tell their partners, with emphasis placed on patient referral as the ideal form of PN. In cases where patients do not feel comfortable conducting PN on their own, HCWs are to assist the patients with PN through whichever medium/ contact information there is, including Facebook and dating apps if necessary. It remains stressed that PN is voluntary and should only be conducted with the patient's consent.

2.1.2 Barriers

Barriers for HIV/STI PN include an increasing number of anonymous partners, a lack of time and staffing, and a lack of evidence of effectiveness of PN making GPs and others reluctant to devote time to the task. Additionally, the lack of a central monitoring system for PN makes auditing effectiveness difficult.

2.1.3 Monitoring

Both diagnosing physicians and laboratories are required by law to notify the Health Protection Surveillance Centre (HPSC) of the diagnosis. There is no central repository for monitoring partner notification. Any information on PN is noted directly in the patient chart. In the past, STI clinics did use a paper contact slip to track partners, but as the slips became more popular and recognizable patients became less interested in using them.

2.1.4 Laws and Guidelines

Ireland follows BASHH and SSHA guidelines, using both patient and provider referral, with the emphasis placed on patient referral where possible. There are no laws that stipulate partner notification of HIV or STIs is compulsory.

CASE EXAMPLE: In March 2018, Republic of Ireland High Court rules refusing to give permission to force teenager to disclose his HIV status. The case was brought to court seeking permission to allow a doctor to disclose the HIV status of a patient, without their consent, to another person the doctor believes the patient is having unprotected sex with. The court concluded that the extremely low possibility (0.04%) of HIV being transmitted in this case, and the fact

that HIV is not a terminal illness, did not justify a breach of patient confidentiality, which is a cornerstone of the doctor/patient relationship. (Source: <http://www.hivireland.ie/hiv-ireland-welcomes-high-court-decision-on-hiv-disclosure/>)

2.2 Viral Hepatitis

While Ireland was previously in a position to eliminate Hepatitis C (HCV), a delayed response has led to an increase in new cases, with recent reports estimating as many as 20,000-50,000 cases unidentified and untreated [2].

2.2.1 Pathways

Similar to HIV/STIs, there is not one unified method or tool for partner notification for viral hepatitis. Similarly, there is no national strategy on how to manage partners/contacts. The current system denotes that the index patient's address designates which local department of health oversees management of the PN process. This design has led to each local Department of Health (DoH) defining their own procedures and pathways. More importantly, when it comes to PN/CT of viral hepatitis, contact tracing was never recommended in Ireland.

When a physician diagnoses the patient, they are required by law to notify the Health Protection Surveillance Centre (HPSC). This notification is then forwarded to the local DoH where the index patient's address is registered. The local DoH then sends a letter to a GP in the area to carry out 'enhanced surveillance'. The letter contains information leaflets for the patient and the GP highlighting the importance of contacting partners, though this is geared towards future partners. The GP's then determine how much time they devote to contact tracing.

The task of contact tracing falls to the GP, yet they receive no extra funding or time for these efforts. In instances when the patient was diagnosed outside of their local DoH jurisdiction, this is particularly troublesome, as the GPs responsible may never have seen the patient before. There are no forms to keep track of contact tracing and no instructions or guidelines to help health care providers navigate the process. It is understood that everyone should do it, but it is up to them if and how they go about it, as there are no consistent methods nor are there instructions/guides to help healthcare workers through the process. Currently, contact tracing for hepatitis is mainly done through phone calls and letters.

2.2.2 Barriers

In Ireland, there is a lack of public health resources for hepatitis partner notification. Even with the ability to make and distribute guidelines or a tool for partner notification, there is not staff available to implement the guidelines or to conduct partner notification using the tool. Particularly in the case of viral hepatitis, which presents in mobile populations, partner notification can take significant time as individuals are difficult to track, requiring more time and funding to dedicate to the task. Even with more resources, there are significant concerns about patient confidentiality and the legal justification behind partner notification, making clinicians hesitant to give information to public health departments. Additionally, stigma remains a significant barrier to patients contacting partners.

HIGHLIGHT: One expert consulted in the mapping process noted that with the high-risk groups that typically present with HCV in Ireland, such as prisoners, people who inject drugs (PWID), migrants, etc, it would be more helpful to have a nurse practitioner involved in partner notification. Not only is this important due to the time it takes to sufficiently counsel patients, but also due to the mixture of clinical and social aspects that accompany high-risk groups, such as language, cultures, temporary living arrangements, etc, that make the task more difficult, which nurses may be more suited to deal with.

2.2.3 Monitoring

Both diagnosing physicians and laboratories are required by law to notify HPSC of the diagnosis. There is currently no monitoring of viral hepatitis contact tracing, and therefore, there is also no auditing. Not even the local DoHs have information on this.

2.2.4 Laws and Guidelines

Ireland is working on a national hepatitis elimination plan, but for the moment there is a national strategy for hepatitis that is in line with the WHO 2030 elimination targets. In 2012, the Health Service Executive published a National Hepatitis C Strategy, and in 2017 they published a National Hepatitis C Screening Guideline. The 'Hepatitis C Screening National Clinical Guideline No.15' includes recommendations for screening of household contacts, sexual partners and more of individuals who are HCV positive. Specifically, Recommendation 13 highlights partner screening of HCV as the following:

13.1. In general, HCV screening of sexual partners of known HCV cases is not recommended in heterosexual couples who are both HIV negative.

13.2. Sexual partners of known HCV cases should be considered for screening in the following situations: a) If the HCV infected case is a PWID b) If the case or contact is also HIV positive.

13.3. Sexual contacts of PWID, but whose HCV status is unknown or where there is evidence of resolved infection, should be considered for screening.

13.4. If testing of a sexual partner of an HCV-infected case is requested for reassurance, then this should not be denied. Partners of HCV-infected PWID may be at increased risk as they may themselves have a history of injecting drug use (IDU), or due to environmental exposure to discarded needles, or they may have been involved in commercial sex work.

2.3 Tuberculosis

In Ireland, TB contact tracing has functioned within public health pathways.

2.3.1 Pathways

Ireland has guidelines that outline the contact tracing protocols for TB in Ireland. It denotes that public health doctors are the only ones that carry out contact tracing for TB (with the one exception of Cork, where a nurse is highly involved with the process). Once a patient is diagnosed, the HPSC is notified by both the diagnosing clinician and the laboratory that examines the samples. Public health officials will first check with the diagnosing GP to ensure that the patient has been told of the diagnosis, and then will hand over the process to a public health GP to perform the contact tracing. The specialized GP will then contact the patient directly, bringing family and close contacts in for screening and heading to work and/or school facilities to carry out screenings.

Despite this, there is no unified process for contact tracing around the country. Instead, the process will be different in different parts of the country, with some areas supporting TB specific clinics, while others do not. Ireland has no clinical program for TB.

2.3.2 Barriers

Many barriers were identified, including a lack of dedicated TB control/ national approach, no resources in the way of money or personnel, and no standardized database of people previously contacted in the contact tracing process. Additionally, in Ireland the disease is particularly high among migrants, and there is the added challenge of language barriers and a mobile population that can be difficult to follow up with.

Due to the nature of screening for TB, the process requires a more in-depth medical background; you cannot separate testing and screening contacts in TB. While in other disease areas, utilizing nurses and/or community resources could prove helpful in improving partner notification/contact tracing, it is difficult to see how community resources could accomplish contact tracing for TB.

2.3.3 Monitoring

Since 2003, TB is mandatorily notifiable to the HPSC by physicians and labs, with the labs using a computerized system to notify public health (HPSC) of the diagnosis. Each local Department of Health keeps their own records, but there is no centralized or standardized database, and therefore no uniform method for monitoring contact tracing. Typically, the number of identified contacts screened for each index case is reported.

CASE EXAMPLE: In Ireland, the public health department uses an information system called Computerized Infectious Disease Reporting (CIDR) to manage the surveillance and control of infectious diseases within the country. The DoH did investigate utilizing the CIDR system for contact tracing but found that the process was too expensive to undertake.

2.3.4 Laws and Guidelines

The HPSC put forth the 'Guidelines on the Prevention and Control of Tuberculosis in Ireland 2010'. There is an entire section (Section 8) devoted to contact tracing. This section includes information on screening, contact investigation and initiating the index case, prioritizing contacts, screening tools and sections on screening in specific environments. It also includes recommendations for monitoring and evaluating contact tracing efforts. Other than surveillance, there are no legal requirements for contact tracing.

2.4 Areas of Potential Integration/ Overlap

It is important to note in Ireland that the historical development of health systems has contributed greatly to the current pathways for partner notification and contact tracing. In each disease area, the local Departments of Health developed their own systems independently from one another, resulting in a variety of methods, processes and monitoring systems in use across the country. Today, there is still a lack of central, streamlined process/method and database for monitoring these processes, and local DoH tailor guidelines to fit their own needs and developed systems. It might be possible to deep-dive into the different local departments to discern if the pathways for PN/CT within disease areas are similar in a local context, with the potential for integration/adaptation across them.

However, based on discussions with our key informants and experts, integrating TB with the other disease areas seems highly difficult. While TB has always functioned within the public health domain with dedicated staff for contact tracing complete with adequate resources, the other disease areas lack this continuity. Despite discussions with these individuals on the topic, the overwhelming response is that the route of transmission of diseases, as well as the division of diseases within the health system, does not lend itself to integrating TB. HIV, STIs and viral hepatitis share similarities enable integration, while TB does not.

In the more densely populated areas of the country, there is dedicated staff to help with the PN/CT in the different disease areas. As the process can require significant time from staff for counselling, checking in and allowing patients time to complete the process as they see fit, it could be worthwhile to create a specialized position in less densely populated areas that handles the PN/CT for all four disease areas. Introducing a nurse or social worker that specializes in partner notification for HIV/STIs, hepatitis, and TB, rather than requiring a different staff member for each disease, is an option that could be explored for rural areas, where the disease areas do not have a similar demand.

A recurring barrier is a lack of time and resources to devote to PN/CT. Key informants in Ireland noted that the Irish model for partner notification in East of the country has the potential to make strides in prevention efforts. With certified course instruction on PN/CT, and in some instances dedicated staff for PN/CT, Ireland could demonstrate the effectiveness of PN/CT. Yet due to high patient loads and limited funding and staff, this remains stymied. While literature notes the importance of partner notification as secondary prevention measure, there is limited evidence to demonstrate its effectiveness, leaving little bargaining power for additional resources from public health. Raising awareness and support for PN/CT from politicians/ influence groups could contribute greatly to improving the results, as could instituting monitoring of these actions.

2.4 Flowchart Ireland

3. Italy

The procedures of partner notification and contact tracing in Italy vary considerably by region and by hospital/centre. There are only national guidelines on contact tracing for TB. Active PN for HIV, STIs, viral hepatitis and Syphilis takes place but is not standardised. There is community-assisted PN for HIV, HCV and syphilis.

3.1 HIV/STIs

3.1.1 Pathways

Patients are diagnosed with HIV in hospitals, public voluntary counselling and testing (VCT) services, community-based voluntary counselling and testing (CBVCT) services, private labs and through self-testing. Some public VCTs, like that of the Infectious Disease outpatient clinic in Verona, are similar to the GUM clinics seen in the UK and offer STI testing. Patients diagnosed with HIV are treated in the Infectious Disease Units. For STIs other than HIV, the dermatological departments treat patients.

Patients diagnosed with HIV are responsible for contacting partners and doctors can play a supportive role. Patients can agree to allow the doctor to inform partners when they are present in the room. The diagnosing doctor is usually more qualified to perform PN for patients who have only one stable partner, compared to patients with multiple casual partners. If the CBVCT employee is appropriately trained, community-assisted PN can be beneficial as it offers an approach closer to the patient.

In Verona and other regions, there are nurses specially trained for counselling in this setting and doctors who manage STI diagnoses and support the patients in doing PN. PN is usually done by phone call or text message, if not in person. Most patients are asked to notify their partners themselves and they generally prefer to do it this way.

3.1.2 Barriers

Respondents reported that the barriers to PN across all diseases were lack of guidelines and lack of standardised procedures. Encouraging the diagnosed person to disclose their status to their partner can be time-consuming. The process is sometimes undertaken in a superficial way, with the clinician not showing enough patience/empathy, which does not make the person keen to disclose. There is a need for more PN training for physicians. The number of professionals in public health, trained in contact tracing of STIs has decreased a lot. In some regions public health workers are responsible for CT, leaving clinicians with more time to dedicate to clinical work.

Completely anonymous partners, mobility and lack of contact details can also be a barrier, particularly with MSM index patients.

Some NGOs have opposed the standardisation of PN for HIV, as they are not convinced there are sufficient guarantees to protect patient confidentiality and stigma resulting from disclosure.

3.1.3 Monitoring

STI diagnoses are reported to local public health units anonymously, and the public health service of the local authority can contact the diagnosing doctor to check that they have carried out PN. If the doctor has not, the local authority can request the name of the diagnosed person and initiate PN themselves. As there is no standardised reporting of PN, the extent to which this regulation is used by public health workers is unknown.. It is probably not homogenous across the country.

3.1.4 Laws and Guidelines

There are no national guidelines for PN of HIV and STIs in Italy. Milan has guidelines on how to follow up potential contacts in the case of a HIV diagnosis. These guidelines include information on the timing and how to perform PN depending on whether the case has single partners or multiple partners. For patients with one steady partner, HIV PN is part of good clinical practice and clinicians routinely perform it.

3.2 Viral Hepatitis

3.2.1 Pathways

People are diagnosed with Hepatitis in hospitals and in public or private laboratories. The patient must be responsible for contacting partners as doctors legally cannot perform PN on their own. Doctors can encourage patients to contact partners and patients have the option to allow the doctor to inform the partner when they are present in the room. PN with the doctor present is limited by the number of rooms and counsellors available.

There may be epidemiological investigations of viral Hepatitis but there are no real PN procedures in place.

3.2.2 Barriers

Barriers to monitoring PN are similar to that of STIs/HIV: lack of guidelines, lack of systems, clinicians' lack of training and experience in PN.

3.2.3 Monitoring

There is no national monitoring of viral hepatitis PN.

3.2.4 Laws and Guidelines

There are no national guidelines or laws for viral hepatitis PN.

3.3 Tuberculosis

3.3.1 Pathways

There is a standardised procedure in place: the infectious disease unit handles the clinical side, sometimes with pulmonology. Contact tracing is handled by local public health, who interview patients and construct a list of contacts. In TB clinics, contact tracing is performed by a health assistant (with a 3-4-year degree and specific training in CT) who is in charge of epidemiological surveillance. Outside of TB clinics, doctors are responsible for CT which adds to their already heavy workload. When TB patients are admitted to the hospital, the assistants come to the ward to complete a survey. Patients give information about their close community and the assistant traces the contacts. Tracing is usually done by phone and the assistant does not perform house visits.

3.3.2 Barriers

Barrier include doctors lacking the time for CT when TB is diagnosed outside of TB clinics.

3.3.3 Monitoring

It is not obligatory to report TB diagnoses. There are some regional initiatives to monitor the effect of contact tracing, but no systematic reporting is in place. Local authorities may keep records on contact tracing.

In Italy, the National Prevention Plan for TB aims to improve contact tracing to have 70% of contacts screened for TB. The National Health Service is run on a regional basis. There are national standards, but different regions have

the responsibility to implement the standards. During 2018, some regions may start to work on reaching the target and having evaluation systems in place.

3.3.4 Laws and Guidelines

There are national guidelines for contact tracing of TB. At the regional level, Lombardia has guidelines on CT of TB.

3.4 Areas of Potential Integration/ Overlap

The TB model of assistants doing CT could work for other diseases – being more flexible and reducing the workload of doctors. The flexible model is particularly useful for TB cases affecting migrants who have specific needs (such as high mobility and more limited access to healthcare).

There is no centralised system for collecting information about PN of any of the diseases. Some public health local services keep their own database but only for registering how many persons are diagnosed and treated. At the regional level, there are attempts to set up a TB database, which is expected to be implemented in 2018. Key informants note that TB has a different historical set-up from the others, which could make it difficult to integrate it with the other diseases.

There is a history of PN in Italy – during the AIDS crisis in the 90s there was a programme of PN with a specifically trained psychiatrist, in collaboration with some IDU services in Italy. Community setting training could be a feasible intervention, by addressing the issue of stigma by involving people from the community. Overall, whether it is physicians or CBVCT employees, additional training is needed to ensure that the PN/CT services are appropriate and beneficial to the patient.

3.5 Flowchart Italy

4. Romania

At the national level, there is healthcare-assisted and community-assisted PN for HIV and TB. There are legal requirements and guidelines on PN only for HIV and TB, but the HIV guidelines have not been updated in eight years.

4.1 HIV/STIs

4.1.1 Pathways

People are diagnosed with HIV in infectious disease hospitals and treated in a specialized ward for HIV. An infectious disease specialist discusses PN with the patient and a psychologist can support partner notification.

People are diagnosed with STIs in dermatology and infectious disease hospitals then treated in the dermatology unit, infectious diseases unit, outpatient unit or at the family doctor. The dermatologist /gynaecology specialist calls the family doctor who traces the sexual contacts, with the patients deciding who should establish contact with the partner. In all cases, the patient decides if partners can be informed, also in the case of: pre-nuptial medical checks, pregnancy monitoring and blood donation.

Counselling at VCT centres in Romania actively promotes disclosure of the diagnosis to partners so they can be tested. The method and/or undertaking of PN is decided by the diagnosed patient. The debate between the public health rights of patients' partners and the patients' confidentiality rights, as well as partner notification in general, is not a topic that is high on any agenda in Romania. The team that offers the initial counselling for patients in VCTs (the specialist physician, the psychologist and the social worker) advising the patient to inform his/her partner about the diagnosis and to persuade the partner to come and test. PN only takes place with the consent of the diagnosed patient. VCTs prefer patient-referral PN to ensure confidentiality.

As there is no legislation on PN, VCTs use the general regulations about confidentiality and data protection (such as the European GDPR). The psychosocial care includes counselling and support in how to disclose the HIV diagnosis to partners.

Existing community-based counselling and testing services in Romania could, in theory, offer community-based PN and associated patient education. In the Romanian context, the doctors diagnosing patients have more specialised knowledge thus they are more competent to carry out PN than public health workers and community health workers.

4.1.2 Barriers

There is trust in doctor-patient confidentiality but patients have concerns about their privacy when disclosing their status. Although health professionals have the training to implement PN, lack of education around HIV/STIs among patients and lack of counselling for patients are also barriers.

For HIV, the legislation protects the confidentiality of the diagnosed person. If the patient does not consent, PN cannot be performed.

4.1.3 Monitoring

Doctors complete the notification of a new case of communicable disease and submit it to the local department of public health. Records of partner notification are kept in the patients' file at the local level and only used locally. The data is only centralized in the counting of people who benefitted from counselling (be it diagnosed people or partners of diagnosed people), but counselling does not necessarily mean partner notification took place. There are no indicator monitoring recommendations.

4.1.4 Laws and Guidelines

Romania has not had an update to the national HIV strategy for at least 8 years and the national HIV program encountered other difficulties due to insufficient funding (that lead to temporary ARV stock outs). Any initiatives on partner notification should also be aligned with the new GDPR requirements (European regulation regarding data protection) that became compulsory in Europe in May 2018.

Ministry of Health Order no. ITS 1342/2014 presents guidelines for diagnosis and treatment of STIs which recommend PN do not make it obligatory and do not give guidelines on how to perform it. The National Guidelines for HIV, updated with Ministry of Health Order no. 377/2017, recommend PN but, again, PN is not obligatory and no indications of how to perform it are in place. There are no guidelines on whether to do patient referral or healthcare-assisted PN. The psychologist, doctor, and social worker are all trained in partner notification and can do it with the consent of patients.

VCTs include PN of HIV in their own guidelines - recommending that HIV positive patients who come for check-ups and support are encouraged to bring their partners as well for HIV testing.

4.2 Viral Hepatitis

4.2.1 Pathways

People are diagnosed with Hepatitis B and C in any clinical laboratory, infectious disease hospitals, gastro-enterology units and then treated in infectious disease hospitals and gastro-enterology units. The patient decides if partner notification takes place and the family doctor can support the PN process.

4.2.2 Barriers

Guidelines for Hepatitis B and C surveillance recommend partner notification, but it is not obligatory to perform it and there are no specific indications are outlined. If the patient agrees, an infectious disease specialist informs the family doctor and gastroenterologist about the diagnosis so that it appears on the patient's medical history.

4.2.3 Monitoring

None

4.2.4 Laws and Guidelines

The Surveillance Methodology for viral hepatitis B and C issued in Jan 2017.

4.3 Tuberculosis

4.3.1 Pathways

People are diagnosed and treated for TB in outpatient or in pneumology hospitals. The methodology for the National TB Program states that contact tracing (CT) is "obligatory for TB" but if the patient does not want to provide contacts there is no legal obligation. The TB outpatient doctor contacts the family doctor or the workplace doctor and notifies them about the newly diagnosed case. The outpatient doctor conducts the epidemiologic inquiry.

4.3.2 Barriers

Lack of human resources and financial resources to perform CT. NGOs have better relationships with vulnerable communities than health services, so they can be a good bridge in the CT process.

4.3.3 Monitoring

A standardised epidemiological survey to be completed by outpatient doctors is in place.

4.3.4 Laws and Guidelines

Methodology for the National TB Program (CT is “obligatory for TB” but if patient does not want to give contacts there is no legal obligation).

4.4 Areas of Potential Integration/Overlap

It was noted that it may not be feasible to integrate TB because of different transmission routes.

The HIV model (guidelines for pre/post HIV counselling issued by the CDC but not explicitly/exclusively for partner notification) can be adapted and scaled up. In VCTs, partners of HIV patients are tested and counselled by members of the psychosocial department, who provide psychosocial care to HIV patients. Although they follow the same procedure as the community VCT teams, offering pre and post-test counselling, the counsellor is the same psychologist/ social worker who is managing the case of the HIV infected partner. This allows a continuity of counselling, testing and monitoring regardless of the HIV test result.

VCTs that offer ART encourage patients to inform their partners of their HIV status and few patients refuse to do so. Due to the fact that patients are seen quarterly or even monthly, the VCTs are able to work through PN with the patient over time.

4.5 Flowchart Romania

5. Greece

A lack of guidelines means it is not clear who has responsibility for PN in the case of each disease. It may be psychosocial scientists, physicians, nurses or lay counsellors (when the person is diagnosed in an NGO).

5.1 HIV/STIs

5.1.1 Pathways

Once diagnosed with HIV or STIs, the doctors in the infectious diseases unit handle the case. Sometimes PN is carried out by public health nurses. PN is generally voluntary, except in extreme cases where a person's refusal to disclose causes the case to be referred to the District Attorney's (DA) office. PN for HIV is performed only with the patient's consent. Psychosocial scientists and health professionals follow the rules and methodology of semi-directive interview, based on techniques of persuasion and psychological support to encourage patients to disclose to their partners. Different methods for PN for HIV are used depending on whether the patient has steady or casual partners. For casual partners, every effort is made to get the patient to work on PN with the healthcare professionals. For steady partners, PN is done by the patient him/herself and healthcare professionals can assist. Preferred method of carrying out PN is in person. Letters, phone calls and emails are not allowed due to data protection laws. Doctors, nursing staff and psychosocial workers are responsible for PN, although this may differ based on region. For example, in Attica, public health nurses and doctors are responsible for PN.

5.1.2 Barriers

The main issue for PN (particularly for HIV) is achieving the balance between the safeguarding of public health, the safeguarding of the patient's medical confidentiality and the safeguarding of the patient's human rights and individual freedoms. In hospital settings, there is no clear documentation in file or registry system that the PN took place. As there is no clinical care pathway for PN, clear legal limits and resources that could guide healthcare workers are lacking.

5.1.3 Monitoring

Since 1993, the Hellenic Centre for Disease Control and Prevention (HCDCP) implements actions related to HIV: field/outreach interventions, harm-reduction, psychosocial services, information provision, pre and post-test counselling, psychological support. In this context, the psychosocial professionals of HCDC carry out the training and the follow-up supervision of Community Based Services (NGOs). Though all the above actions and interventions are recorded and reported in annual reports, PN is not necessarily monitored.

5.1.4 Laws and Guidelines

There are very limited guidelines on PN (Counselling about HIV Infection, WHO (1990); Prevention of sexual transmission of human immunodeficiency virus, WHO (1990); MoH circular (2000)). Guidelines promote patient-led PN of HIV, and PN without patient consent only as a last resort after referring the case to the Committee of Legal Support and Legal Problems of HCDCP (see *Article 104* below). The patient is informed on the importance and ethical obligation he/she has to inform his/her partner/s but no clear/specific health system procedure is followed.

Article 103. Neither Physicians nor any other person have the right to notify the spouse or sexual partner of an HIV positive person as to the status of that person's health to protect them from the risk of infection. Providing every psychological and social means of support, it is preferred that the same person who is HIV positive be encouraged to act so that the spouse or partner may be protected.

Article 104. If the HIV positive person is not persuaded to inform either the spouse or the sexual partner of his/her infection with HIV, then, having exhausted all means of persuasion, the physician may resort to the Committee of Legal Support and Legal Problems of the HCDCP or to the public prosecutor, who, after having verified that the necessary conditions exist, may grant permission for notification.

PN is affected by the Law on the Management of Sensitive Personal Data, such as health data (2492/1997), and the Law on Medical Ethics (3418/2005). However, after May 28th, 2018, the health data law became invalid due to European wide GDPR requirements. According to these, health workers are not allowed to inform the partner/s of the patient of their diagnosis. The doctors as well as the psychologists discuss with the patient on the need of partner notification in order to persuade him/her to complete it. The doctor of the unit usually informs the partners after the patient has given consent.

CASE EXAMPLE: One case of a patient with HIV refusing to inform the partner of his seropositivity, prompting healthcare professionals dealing with the case to consider the prosecutors intervention and the notification of the relevant HCDCP consultants. However, through semi directive interviews and intensive psychological support the patient changed his approach.

CASE EXAMPLE: The full impact of border closure on migrant health remains to be seen, and the lack of PN framework and resources will further impact the health of these and other vulnerable populations.

5.2 Viral Hepatitis

5.2.1 Pathways

For HBV and HCV persons are diagnosed in hospitals, blood donation units, infectious disease units, dermatology-venerology departments, and private laboratories. Patients are then treated in hospitals and outpatient clinics. There are no guidelines on PN of viral hepatitis.

5.2.2 Barriers

Barriers to PN include the stigma of having a disease, the lack of guidelines on PN, the lack of specific legislation on PN, language and cultural barriers (for migrants), the lack of personnel, the lack of training for personnel on interviewing or empowering patients. The legal framework around sensitive personal data prevents an IT system being put in place which is a barrier to effective PN.

5.2.3 Monitoring

No monitoring of viral hepatitis PN.

5.2.4 Laws and Guidelines

The laws governing medical ethics and protection of data noted in the HIV/STI section are the same as those that impact PN of viral hepatitis.

5.3 Tuberculosis

5.3.1 Pathways

When a case of TB is diagnosed, clinical and laboratory physicians are responsible for the completion of the TB notification form, which is then sent to the Department of Epidemiological Surveillance and Intervention of the HCDCP. The HCDCP shares available information with the Public Health Directorate of the local prefecture (PHD).

HCDCP monitors and evaluates TB epidemiological data whereas PHDs are responsible for local public health action and conducting TB contact tracing (including partner notification). Phone calls are used only to inform potentially exposed persons for the need to be evaluated for TB. Contact through e-mails concerning sensitive personal data are not allowed in Greece according to the law 2492/1997 and GDPR since May 2018. There is an obligation to inform and test everybody potentially exposed. PN is usually done in person. In the case that the patient does not consent to PN, the DA's office is involved.

5.3.2 Barriers

Barriers include the lack of a national registry of TB and data protection laws that restrict the methods of contacting partners/people at risk. Marginalised populations are the most at-risk of TB infection. Shortage of resources and trained personnel lead to an absence of Directly Observed Treatment programmes, hampering contact tracing procedures and latent TB treatment use among migrants, refugees, homeless people, ex-prisoners and PWIDs (see case study).

CASE STUDY: The "Sotiria" Chest Diseases Hospital in central Athens sees some of the most vulnerable TB patients but lack the capacity and resources to retain people in inpatient and outpatient care. As migrants constitute a sizeable proportion of TB patients, there is often a language barrier with staff. Any contact tracing processes are complicated by patients' lack of stable housing. Some patients end up homeless, interrupt their treatment and increase the risk of spreading the disease. The benefits of contact tracing for TB are limited if the patient does not complete treatment and continues to spread the infection. Systems with waivers for transportation, food or even money incentives to present for Directly Observed Treatment for TB could be very cost-effective and improve the impact of CT.

5.3.3 Monitoring

The HCDCP holds the national TB registry, however there is no official registry of TB PN. The personnel of the Department of Epidemiological Surveillance and Intervention of the HCDCP performs follow up phone calls to ensure all close contacts of infectious or possibly infectious TB cases are referred for evaluation for TB. Any CT procedures are recorded, as well as results of tests and x-rays.

5.3.4 Laws and Guidelines

PN is affected by the GDPR (previously the law on the management of sensitive personal data such as health data (2492/1997)) and the law on medical ethics (3418/2005). Due to this, phone calls are used to invite potentially exposed persons to be evaluated. Contact through e-mails containing sensitive personal data are not allowed, so notification is usually done in person. In the extreme case the patient does not consent, the doctor or the public health nurse refers the case to the District Attorney's office.

5.4 Areas of Potential Integration/Overlap

Historically HIV, Hepatitis and STI treatment and monitoring are kept separate from TB. Integrating TB and HIV PN could be the most coherent, particularly as clinicians are aware that the crisis in Greece could cause a resurgence of TB cases among PWID living with HIV. Legal restrictions to protect patient confidentiality present significant hurdles in Greece, and since the onset of the GDPR, the entirety of Europe. Laws on when and how patients' partners can be contacted by HCWs act as significant barriers to those approaching the PN process. Understanding the scope of these laws is crucial for HCWs to feel confident in the services that they are legally able to provide.

KEELPNO's collaboration with community-based organisations involved in actions against HIV/AIDS could be an opportunity to implement PN training for community-based organisations. The NGO 'Positive Voice' is looking at setting up a HIV PN pilot study. In Greece, settings where HIV screening tests are performed, including CBVCT sites,

are not allowed to conduct confirmatory tests. Only HIV reference centers are dedicated to do these. Therefore, no person could be considered as HIV (+) cases without confirmatory testing. This should be taken into consideration when designing a pilot study, as persons with HIV reactive results should first be referred for confirmatory testing followed by other health care services.

There already exists an electronic platform of TB drug prescriptions which could be utilised for PN of TB, although data protection laws must be taken into consideration carefully.

5.5 Flowchart Greece

6. Conclusions

This report maps the variety of healthcare settings and pathways in which partner notification and contact tracing take place in Ireland, Italy, Romania and Greece across the four disease areas. While some findings are country and/or disease area specific, there were many findings that were echoed across settings and disease areas. The following findings must be given consideration before planning the pilot studies.

Monitoring PN/CT remains a challenge. Not only do confidentiality laws and requests for anonymity make it difficult to audit the effectiveness of PN, but also there are difficulties surrounding data protection with new GDPR requirements. Additionally, a national registry of PN is not feasible in countries where there is no national registry of said disease.

A recurring barrier seen across sites and disease areas was a lack of time and resources to appropriately conduct partner notification and contact tracing. Regardless of the staff devoted to the task, it appears that the time-consuming nature of partner notification, as well as the high number of patients, results in a lack of adequate time to devote to PN in the manner that is recommended. Several respondents noted that the use of community facilities or CBVCT centers for partner notification could be a potential option. Outsourcing the activity and increasing the number of staff available to assist the process could see positive results, if the staff involved with PN/CT were well trained.

Another barrier encountered in the mapping process is a general confusion surrounding the 'how it works' of partner notification. Despite interviewing key informants in a position to be well versed in the knowledge of how the system of PN works, interviewees were not always clear about the guidelines, pathways, and monitoring of the activity. Some informants referred to PN guidelines embedded in other documents but could not locate these when asked. Nor were they clear if and how partner notification was taking place. In some countries, this confusion is compounded by a lack of uniform set-up for partner notification within different regions/ areas of the country. For example, in Ireland, each of the local departments of health acted independently, forming their own pathways and methods for partner notification. In Italy, some regions have created their own guidelines for partner notification, while others may utilize international guidelines or not specify any at all.

Interviews suggest that increased training and awareness of partner notification could improve outcomes. In Greece, there are laws that protect patient confidentiality that make healthcare workers feel less confident in what aspects of partner notification they are legally allowed to counsel and assist patients. Since the advent of the GDPR in May 2018, other European countries may also experience barriers related to patient confidentiality. An increased knowledge and awareness of these laws could improve healthcare worker confidence, encouraging more patients to conduct partner notification with increased support. Additionally, increased training on how to counsel and support patients to conduct partner notification on their own and increased training on well-established or local guidelines for partner notification is necessary for healthcare workers if they are expected to lead partner notification efforts. While healthcare settings differ across the pilot countries, as do the pathways that partner notification follows in different disease areas, training on how to conduct partner notification could be applied in a variety of settings.

The aim of the Integrate JA is to integrate the four different disease areas, HIV, STIs, viral hepatitis and TB. This report hoped to highlight areas for potential integration in partner notification/contact tracing. Through interviews, it emerged that while HIV, STIs and in some instances viral hepatitis could be integrated without significant systemic changes, TB is a vastly different case. In most settings, TB care and the contact tracing that accompanies it, have pathways set in separate institutions from the other disease areas. While HIV, STIs and viral hepatitis are often within infectious diseases, TB tends to be housed in pneumology. As the mode of transmission for TB is significantly

different than that of the other disease areas, it follows that the contact tracing efforts for TB must be structured in a different method as well. For this reason, the key informants unanimously noted that it would be difficult, and perhaps unwarranted, to try to integrate TB contact tracing into the partner notification efforts of the other disease areas. And while the differences are many, the interviews demonstrate that TB is typically the most developed PN/CT programme out of all the diseases, with a history of established pathways and national guidelines, offering the potential to learn from TB CT for other disease areas. Offering training for TB contact tracing may still be applicable to improve outcomes but finding one uniform method of partner notification/ contact tracing across the four disease areas is unlikely to affect change.

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Abbreviations

- CBVCT Community-based Voluntary Counselling and Testing
- CIDR Computerized Infectious Disease Reporting
- CT contact tracing
- DA District Attorney
- DoH Department of Health
- GP general practitioner
- HCV Hepatitis C
- HCW healthcare Worker
- HPSC Health Protection Surveillance Centre
- IDU injecting drug use
- PN partner notification
- PN/CT partner notification/ contact tracing
- PWID people who inject drugs
- VCT Voluntary Counselling and Testing

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Croatian association for HIV and viral hepatitis

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